

A new species of *Thylacella* Enderlein, 1911 (Psocoptera: Lepidopsocidae) with an identification key to the species from Africa and Madagascar

Dilian Georgiev

Department of Ecology and Environmental Conservation, University of Plovdiv, 24 Tsar Assen Street, 4000 Plovdiv, Bulgaria, diliangeorgiev@gmail.com

<http://zoobank.org/C5A11454-F12A-4CC7-BF94-29E047018D8A>

Abstract: A new species of *Thylacella* was collected from Unguja Island (Zanzibar, Tanzania) and described in this paper. A simple identification key is also proposed for all the species known from Africa and Madagascar. Now from this genus a total of 19 recent and two fossil species are known.

Keywords: Africa, identification key, Madagascar, new species, Psocoptera

Introduction

The genus *Thylacella* Enderlein, 1911 (Psocoptera, Lepidopsocidae) is comprised of 18 recent and two fossil species. The type species of the genus was described from Holocene copal from Zanzibar by Enderlein (1911). Later 16 new recent species were found in Central and East Africa and Madagascar (Badonnel 1949, 1955, 1967, 1969, 1973, Smithers 1964, Broadhead & Richards 1982), one from Cuba (Banks 1941), and one from South America (García Aldrete 2001).

A new species of *Thylacella* was collected from Unguja Island (Zanzibar, Tanzania) and described in this paper. A simple identification key is also proposed for all the species known from Africa and Madagascar.

Material and methods

Psocoptera were collected from the east coast of Unguja Island – at the north part of Michamwi Peninsula by beating the vegetation. The specimens were stored in 96% ethanol.

The photos (specimens in glycerin) were taken by a camera Canon PowerShot SX500IS through the eyepiece of a light microscope Optika.

Type material was deposited at the National Museum of Natural History (NMNH) – Sofia, Bulgaria.

The species discussed in the paper were considered according to original descriptions, redescrptions, and published identification keys (Enderlein 1911, Badonnel 1949, 1955, 1967, 1969, 1973, Broadhead & Richards 1982).

Measurements abbreviations: LC = body length; F+tr = hind femur and trochanter length; T = hind tibia length; t1, t2, t3 = tarsomeres of hindtarsus (lengths measured from condyle to condyle), FW = forewing, HW = hindwing.

Results and discussion

Reexaminations of *Thylacella* specimens erroneously reported as *Thylacella angustipennis* Broadhead & Richards, 1982 by Georgiev (2021) for Unguja Island revealed that they belong to a new species to science.

Fig. 1. *Thylacella zanzibarica* n. sp., female, paratype: A – lateral view, B – dorsal view, C – forewing, D – hindwing (pigmentation shown by an arrow), F – apex of the lacinia, E – side view of the head (F and E not to scale). Photographed in glycerin, after 11 months in ethanol.

Thylacella zanzibarica n. sp.

Material examined: Holotype: 1 ♀, from the type locality, 5.3.2021, NMNH – Sofia, Bulgaria; paratype: 1 ♀, from the type locality, 5.3.2021, NMNH – Sofia, Bulgaria.

Type locality: Tanzania, Zanzibar, Unguja Island, Michamwi Peninsula, sandy coastal area with scrubs, from a pile of old palm leaf mats, S06 07 55.5 E39 29 31.2, 6 m a. s. l.

Description. Female. Colouration. The whole body is light brown in freshly preserved specimens (Fig. 2, A), and turning brown-yellowish after time (Fig. 1, A, B). The eyes are black. The head is light brown (lighter than the thorax and the abdomen) with a darker lateral band on each side from anterior margin of the eye to the antennal socket (Fig. 1, A, E). Thorax brown. Abdomen brown with darker transverse bands on each tergite. Forewing pale brownish with lighter middle part, where some darker pigment is located at Sc and the distal part of the central cell. A fuzzy dark transverse stripe forms at the distal half of the wing, followed by another paler section. All veins pale, but a little darker than the membrane (Fig. 1, C). Hindwing in most of its

part colourless but having a very pale brown irregular stripe at its upper periphery. This band is much thicker between veins R1 and R2+3 (Fig. 1, D).

Morphology. Head densely setosae. The apex of the lacinial pick is broadened and having two denticles, a longer and a shorter one. The longer one is bearing an apex with two small cusps (Fig. 1, F). Pretarsal claws with a preapical tooth and with a minute denticle near middle of the claw (Fig. 2, D). Wings with long hairs and without scales, moderately pointed. The nodulus of the forewing consists of truncated spines set close together. In hindwing M1 and M2 arise separately from Rs (Fig. 1, D). The gonapophyses slightly sclerotised at the base and with very long hairs (Fig. 2, C). Paraprocts with strong spurs each (Fig. 2, B).

Measurements. Holotype (female): LC = 1.66 mm, t1 = 0.29 mm, t2 = 0.04, t3 = 0.05 mm, T = 0.75 mm, F+tr = 0.54 mm, FW = 1.6 mm, HW not measured (as not to violate the integrity of the holotype); Paratype (female): LC = 1.94 mm, head = 0.6 mm, hind leg: t1 = 0.3 mm, t2 and t3 both = 0.03 mm, T = 0.8 mm, F+tr = 0.5 mm, FW = 1.58 mm, HW = 1.24 mm.

Diagnosis. The presence of pigmentation on the hindwing discerns the new species from most of the

Fig. 2. *Thylacella zanzibarica* n. sp., female, paratype: A – dorsal view when freshly preserved (by Georgiev, 2021), B – spine of the paraproct, C – lateral view of the gonapophysis, D – claw with t3 (C and B not to scale). Photographed in glycerin.

Fig. 3. Habitat and microhabitat of *Thylacella zanzibarica* n. sp.: coastal scrubs at the type locality (left) and an old pile of dry mats made from palm leaves on the ground (right).

species from the genus which have hyaline wing membrane. Similar light pigmented band on the upper hindwing periphery present in *T. montana* Badonnel, 1967 from Madagascar, but this species have less pointed brown forewings (Badonnel, 1967).

In external view, having relatively uniformly brown body and striped wings, *T. zanzibarica* n. sp. is

similar with *T. congolensis* (Badonnel, 1949) (Congo, Nigeria, Togo), *T. fasciata* Badonnel, 1955 (Angola, Congo, Mozambique, Nigeria, Tanzania, Zimbabwe) and *T. angustipennis* Broadhead & Richards, 1982 (Kenya). From *T. congolensis* it differs by the longer hairs of the gonapophyses, more pointed wings, and the tip of the lacinia; from *T. fasciata* by the curved and

tilted back Sc (in *fasciata* it is straight or just a little tilted back), lack of two large brown spots on the vertex and not so clear brown bands on the forewing; from *T. angustipennis* differs by its less pointed wings and the tip of the lacinia.

The new species is similar in appearance and with the fossil *T. eversiana* Enderlein, 1911 (type species of the genus), described from Holocene copal from Zanzibar too. From this species (possible ancestor?) *T. zanzibarica* n. sp. differs by the venation of the hindwing. In the new species M2 is as long as M1, and not connected with it. In *T. eversiana* M2 is shorter and connects to M1. Both species differ and by their forewing venation – cells r3 and m1 are much shorter in the new species.

Habitat. The species was collected from a pile of dry old mats made from palm leaves on the sand among coastal scrubs (Fig. 3).

Identification key to the recent and fossil species of the genus *Thylacella* known from Africa and Madagascar

- 1. Wings with pointed apex 2.
- Wings with rounded apex *T. fenestrata* Smithers, 1964
- 2. Hindwing vein M2 is shorter and connected to M1 3.
- Hindwing vein M2 is longer and is not connected to M1 5.
- 3. Head with a specific x-like pattern on frons *T. angulifrons* Badonnel, 1967
- Head colour different 4.
- 4. Forewing uniformly brownish *T. madagascariensis* Smithers, 1964
- Forewing with a darker transverse stripe *T. eversiana* Enderlein, 1911
- 5. Forewings strongly pointed 6.
- Forewings moderately pointed 10.
- 6. Forewings hyaline *T. vitripennis* Badonnel, 1967
- Forewings with pigmentation 7.
- 7. Forewings uniformly light brown 8.
- Forewing with darker transverse stripe 9.
- 8. Lacinia widely broadens at its distal part, larger denticle with 3 cusps *T. acutipennis* Badonnel, 1967
- Lacinia slightly broadens at its distal part, larger denticle with 2 cusps *T. immaculata* Badonnel, 1955

- 9. Apex of the lacinia narrow, denticles gathered close each other *T. angustipennis* Broadhead & Richards, 1982
- Apex of the lacinia broad, denticles not gathered close each other *T. fasciata* Badonnel, 1955
- 10. Vertex smoothly concave in the middle, eyes protruding to the side *T. fasciifrons* Badonnel, 1967
- Vertex and eyes normal 11.
- 11. Head with characteristic reticulated pattern *T. annulata* Badonnel, 1976
- Head coloration different 12.
- 12. Head with anchor like pattern on frons *T. trifurcata* Badonnel, 1976
- Head coloration different 13.
- 13. Foreings uniformly brownish *T. montana* Badonnel, 1967
- Forewing with darker transverse stripe 14.
- 14. Hindwing with pale brown pigmentation on its front periphery *T. zanzibarica* n. sp.
- Hindwing hyaline 15.
- 15. Forewing cell r5 not extending the tip of cell m2 *T. pilipennis* (Enderlein, 1912)
- Forewing cell r5 extending over the tip of cell m2 16.
- 16. Gonapophyses with long hairs *T. similis* Badonnel, 1967
- Gonapophyses with relatively short hairs *T. congolensis* (Badonnel, 1949)

Acknowledgements

I am grateful to MSc Ramesh Gurusamy (Southern Regional Centre, Zoological Survey of India, Chennai) for the Badonnel’s papers on Angola sent, and to Prof. Dimitar Bechev for the photographic and microscope equipment, and the long years of support.

References

Badonnel A. 1949 Psocopteres du Congo belge (3^e note). Institut Royal des Sciences Naturelles de Belgique, Bulletin 25 (11): 1–64.
 Badonnel A. 1955 Psocopteres de l’Angola. Publicações culturais da Companhia de Diamantes de Angola 26: 1–267.

- Badonnel A. 1967 Insectes Psocoptères. Faune de Madagascar 23: 1–235.
- Badonnel A. 1969 Psocoptères de l'Angola et de pays voisins, avec revision de types africains d'Enderlein (1902) et de Ribaga (1911). Publicações culturais da Companhia de Diamantes de Angola 79: 15–152.
- Badonnel A. 1973 Psocoptères de l'Angola. IV. Publicações culturais da Companhia de Diamantes de Angola 87: 63–103.
- Banks N. 1941 New Neuropteroid insects from the Antilles. Memorias de la Sociedad Cubana de Historia Natural 15 (4): 385–402.
- Broadhead E., Richards A. 1982 The Psocoptera of East Africa – a taxonomic and ecological survey. Biological Journal of the Linnean Society 17: 137–216.
- Enderlein G. 1911 Die fossilen Copeognathen und ihre Phylogenie. Palaeontographica. Beitrage zur Naturgeschichte der Vorzeit 58.
- García Aldrete A.N. 2001 A second sexual, Western Hemisphere species of *Thylacella* Enderlin (Insecta: Psocoptera: Lepidopsocidae). Reichenbachia 34 (6): 57–60.
- Georgiev D. 2021 On the fauna of Psocoptera of Unguja (Zanzibar) Island (Tanzania, East Africa). Historia naturalis bulgarica 42: 35–42.
<https://doi.org/10.48027/hnb.42.061>
- Smithers C. 1964 On the Psocoptera of Madagascar. Revue de Zoologie et de Botanique africaines 70 (3–4): 209–294.
-